

Multigroup importance function calculation method in the MCU code*

Daniil M. Arkhangelsky¹, Yuliya S. Daichenkova¹, Mikhail A. Kalugin¹, Dmitry S. Oleynik¹, Denis A. Shkarovsky¹

¹ NRC “Kurchatov institute”, 1 Kurchatov Sq., 123182 Moscow, Russia

Corresponding author: Daniil M. Arkhangelsky (arkhangelskiy_dm@nrcki.ru)

Academic editor: Yury Korovin ♦ Received 13 February 2025 ♦ Accepted 17 October 2025 ♦ Published 27 March 2026

Citation: Arkhangelsky DM, Daichenkova YuS, Kalugin MA, Oleynik DS, Shkarovsky DA (2026) Multigroup importance function calculation method in the MCU code. Nuclear Energy and Technology 12(1): 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.12.191438>

Abstract

The calculation of neutron kinetics functionals, including the effective fraction of delayed neutrons (β_{eff}) and the prompt neutron generation time (Λ), by the Monte Carlo method is known to be challenging due to the complexities involved in calculating the adjoint function. In the context of the Monte Carlo method, it is optimal to represent the importance function as the asymptotic number of descendants of a neutron placed at a given point in phase space. In practice, it is possible to consider only a finite number of generations. This limitation forms the basis of the Iterated Fission Probability (IFP) method. However, this approach is associated with several disadvantages, including the convergence of the adjoint source through a given number of generations, the appearance of statistical noise, and high memory consumption. In this paper, we present a methodology for calculating the multigroup importance function using the matrix method implemented in the MCU code. The computational model is partitioned into a finite number of tally objects and energy groups. During the modeling process, the elements of the fission matrix are tallied, and the neutron importance function for each energy group of each object is calculated at the post-processing stage. The methodology was validated by calculating β_{eff} and Λ for 6 ICSBEP Handbook experiments. The one- and 14-group approximation of the importance function yielded almost identical results, with a negligible difference (less than 1%), due to the minor change in importance in the energy range where most neutrons are generated.

Keywords

fission matrix, kinetic parameters, matrix method, MCU, Monte Carlo method, neutron importance function

Introduction

In the domain of nuclear power plant safety analysis, the neutron kinetics parameters, namely the effective fraction of delayed neutrons (β_{eff}) and the prompt neutron generation time (Λ), are of particular significance. These functionals are generally weighted, i.e. when calculating them it is necessary to take into account the adjoint flux. The estimation of the latter using the Monte Carlo method requires

reverse modelling of histories (Hoogenboom 2003), which presents significant difficulties. In the context of the Monte Carlo method it is more optimal to represent the adjoint function as the asymptotic number of descendants of a neutron placed at a certain point in phase space.

In practice it is only possible to model a finite number of generations, which formed the basis of the IFP (Iterated Fission Probability) method (Hurwitz 1964). It was first implemented in (Frank-Kamenetsky and

* Russian text published: Izvestiya vuzov. Yadernaya Energetika (ISSN 0204-3327), 2025, n. 4, pp. 148–159.

Yudkevich 1971): the contribution to the tally made by the progenitor of the chain is weighted by the generation density achieved after a certain number of hidden generations. This approach in various forms has been implemented in a large number of Monte Carlo codes including MCNP (Kiedrowski et al. 2011), Serpent 2 (Leppänen et al. 2014), RMC (Qiu et al. 2017), SCALE (Perfetti et al. 2017), KIR (Belousov et al. 2024), and OpenMC (Peng et al. 2019).

The disadvantages of the IFP method include high requirements for RAM (large systems may require more than 100 GB of RAM (Perfetti et al. 2017)), difficulties in estimating the number of hidden generations required to achieve asymptotic (Kiedrowski et al. 2011), and the accumulation of statistical noise (Kiedrowski et al. 2011; Leppänen et al. 2014). The latter two circumstances are most pronounced in weakly coupled systems, where a significant number of hidden generations is required to ensure convergence of the adjoint source leading to the accumulation of large statistical uncertainties (Peng et al. 2017).

In certain instances the most effective course of action is to reduce IFP to NFP (Next Fission Probability). This adjustment results in the calculation of the value based on the fission density (Meulekamp et al. 2006) or the neutron generation density (Nauchi et al. 2010) in the subsequent generation. A comparison of the two variations of NFP with the experiment reveals a high degree of agreement (Nagaya et al. 2010).

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \iiint G(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \psi(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0) d\mathbf{r}_0 dE_0 d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \quad (1)$$

where $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ and $\psi(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0)$ are the neutron flux and neutron generation density, respectively

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E) = \frac{\chi(E)}{4\pi} \iint v_f \Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E') \varphi(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) dE' d\boldsymbol{\Omega} \quad (2)$$

$\chi(E)$ – neutron generation spectrum, and $G(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ – Green's function, which determines the neutron flux caused at point $(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ in phase space by a point source located at $(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0)$.

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, E) = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \iint \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) \psi(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0) d\mathbf{r}_0 dE_0 \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E)$ is a Green's function, averaged by angles and energies:

$$\mathbf{T}(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) = \iiint \frac{\chi(E)}{4\pi} v_f \Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E') G(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) d\boldsymbol{\Omega} dE' d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \quad (4)$$

It can be demonstrated that analogous calculations can be repeated for the adjoint integral equation (Carney et al. 2014):

$$\varphi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \iiint G^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0) d\mathbf{r}_0 dE_0 d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \quad (5)$$

where, considering the reciprocity property for the direct and adjoint Green's functions (Bell and Glasstone 1974)

$$G^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = G(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega} \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0) \quad (6)$$

Another class of methods is predicated on a priori calculation of the importance function, with its subsequent tabulation in the code, which implies dividing the system into a finite number of tally objects. The calculation of the adjoint function in this case is possible both by the IFP algorithm and by using the matrix method (Carney et al. 2014; Peng et al. 2019), which is free from the disadvantages inherent in IFP. This approach is implemented in the MCU code (Gurevich et al. 2019).

This algorithm is well suited for systems with good moderation properties in which after several scatterings neutrons enter the thermal region, where v_f is weakly dependent on energy. Thus, neutrons born with different energies have similar importance. In systems with a fast energy spectrum neutron production and absorption energies differ little, and the dependence of v_f on energy is strongly pronounced in the energy range above 1 MeV. In this regard, it is interesting to evaluate the effect of taking into account the energy distribution of the importance function for such systems.

The present work is dedicated to the implementation of a novel methodology for calculating the importance function in a multi-group approximation within the MCU code.

Method

The methodology is developed by starting with the transport equation written in integral form (Carney et al. 2014):

Multiply both sides of equation (1) by $\chi(E)v_f \Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E')/4\pi$ and integrate over angles $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ and energies E' :

we obtain an expression for the adjoint generation density:

$$\psi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E) = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \iint \mathbf{T}^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0) d\mathbf{r}_0 dE_0 \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{T}^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) = \iiint v_f \Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E) G(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega} \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_0, E_0, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_0) \frac{\chi(E')}{4\pi} d\boldsymbol{\Omega} dE' d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_0 \quad (8)$$

This implies an important reciprocity property for operators:

$$\mathbf{T}^\dagger(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{r}, E \rightarrow \mathbf{r}_0, E_0) \quad (9)$$

In order to apply this technique within the Monte Carlo method it is necessary to formulate a discrete representation for equations (3) and (7). The phase space is to be divided into M registration objects and N energy groups.

$$T_{ij}^{ab} = \int_{E \in E_a} dE \int_{\mathbf{r} \in V_i} d\mathbf{r} \int_{E_0 \in E_b} dE_0 \int_{\mathbf{r}_0 \in V_j} T(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0 \rightarrow \mathbf{r}, E) \frac{\psi(\mathbf{r}_0, E_0)}{\psi_j^b} d\mathbf{r}_0 \quad (13)$$

$$\psi_j^b = \int_{E'' \in E_b} dE'' \int_{\mathbf{r}'' \in V_j} \psi(\mathbf{r}'', E'') d\mathbf{r}'' \quad (14)$$

In matrix form, the set of equations (12) can be represented as follows

$$k_{eff} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi^1 \\ \vdots \\ \Psi^N \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi^1 \\ \vdots \\ \Psi^N \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

where the element ψ_i^a of vector Ψ^a is defined as the neutron generation density in group a and object i , whilst operator \mathbf{T} is represented as a block matrix

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{T}^{11} & \dots & \mathbf{T}^{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{T}^{N1} & \dots & \mathbf{T}^{NN} \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{T}^{ab} = \begin{pmatrix} T_{11}^{ab} & \dots & T_{1M}^{ab} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ T_{M1}^{ab} & \dots & T_{MM}^{ab} \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

where element T_{ij}^{ab} represents the probability that a neutron born in the tally object j and energy group b will induce fission within object i , and the energy of the born neutron will lie within the interval a .

From a mathematical perspective, block decomposition can be regarded as a method of structuring data. It does not, however, affect the properties of the matrix as a linear operator. Consequently, the task of finding the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of such a matrix is equivalent to the task for a regular (non-block) matrix of dimension $NM \times NM$ (Ilyin and Poznyak 1999).

In consideration of property (9) the adjoint equation can be expressed as follows:

$$k_{eff} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi^{1\dagger} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi^{N\dagger} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{T}^T \begin{pmatrix} \Psi^{1\dagger} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi^{N\dagger} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$V_i = \{\mathbf{V} : \mathbf{r} \in V_i\} \quad (10)$$

$$E_a = \{E : E_a \leq E < E_{a+1}\} \quad (11)$$

In this case, equation (3) can be written as

$$\psi_i^a = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{b=1}^N T_{ij}^{ab} \psi_j^b \quad (12)$$

where element ψ_j^b of the eigenvector Ψ^b corresponds to the importance of the neutron born in object j and energy group b .

Therefore, in practice the methodology can be summarised as follows: during the modelling process a fission matrix \mathbf{T} is formed. Then, during the post-processing stage the principal eigenvector of the transposed matrix \mathbf{T}^T is calculated.

The resulting importance function can then be utilised to calculate the effective fraction of delayed neutrons and the prompt neutron generation time (Gurevich et al. 2019):

$$\beta_{eff} = \frac{(\Psi^\dagger, \mathbf{B}\Psi)}{(\Psi^\dagger, \mathbf{T}\Psi)} \quad (19)$$

$$\Lambda = \frac{(\Psi^\dagger, \tau \mathbf{T}\Psi)}{(\Psi^\dagger, \mathbf{T}\Psi)} \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{B} is delayed neutron generation operator and τ is a neutron lifetime.

Calculation models

In order to validate the calculation method, calculations were performed for six critical experiments from the ICSBEP Handbook (Paxton 1981). These experiments differed in both fuel composition and the presence or absence of a reflector:

- HMF001 – sphere made of metallic uranium (94% ^{235}U);
- PMF001 – sphere made of metallic plutonium (95% ^{239}Pu);
- U3MF001 – sphere made of metallic ^{233}U (98% ^{233}U);
- HMF028 – sphere made of metallic uranium (93% ^{235}U) with a natural uranium reflector;
- PMF006 – sphere made of metallic plutonium (94% ^{239}Pu) with a natural uranium reflector;
- U3MF006 – sphere made of metallic ^{233}U (98% ^{233}U) with a natural uranium reflector.

Calculation results and discussion

When performing calculations by means of the matrix method, a problem arises in terms of spatial-energy detailing of the importance function: for example, the averaging over sufficiently wide energy ranges leads to distortion of the results, while averaging over too narrow ones leads to the appearance of statistical noise and increased memory consumption.

The work (Arkhangelsky et al. 2023) is devoted to issues of spatial partitioning. Calibration calculations performed with energy division corresponding to ABBN (Abagyan et al. 1981) demonstrated a negligible density of neutron generation with energy less than 2.15 keV, on the basis of which the primary calculations were performed in a 14-group approximation. Nevertheless, the methodology for estimating the level of spatial and energy detail of the importance function required for calculations needs separate study.

The obtained profiles of the energy component of the importance function are consistent with expectations (Nagaya et al. 2010) as illustrated in Fig. 1. The presence of an extremum is explained by the superposition of two effects: firstly, an increase in energy leads to a rise in the value of ν_p , and secondly, neutrons born with low energies are more likely to cause fission.

For variants with a reflector a shift in the importance function to an energy range of more than 1 MeV is observed as one approaches the periphery. This shift is attributed

Figure 1. Energy dependence. **A.** Neutron importance function; **B.** Macroscopic fission cross section; **C.** Fission neutron yield.

Table 1. Comparison of calculated and experimental data

Experiment	β_{eff}				Λ			
	E, 10^{-5}	C_0/E	C_1/E	C_{14}/E	E, 10^{-9} s	C_0/E	C_1/E	C_{14}/E
HMF001	645 ± 13	0.98	0.99	0.99	5.8 ± 0.16	0.99	0.99	0.99
PMF001	190 ± 4	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.0 ± 0.08	0.96	0.94	0.94
U3MF001	289 ± 7	1.01	1.01	1.01	2.9 ± 0.08	1.00	0.98	0.98
HMF028	665 ± 13	0.93	1.03	1.03	17.5 ± 0.57	1.08	1.00	1.00
PMF006	276 ± 7	0.97	1.04	1.04	12.9 ± 0.44	1.20	1.01	1.01
U3MF006	360 ± 9	0.95	1.04	1.04	13.5 ± 0.42	1.12	0.95	0.95

to the threshold nature of the fission cross section of the reflector material – ^{238}U . This phenomenon is most evident at the boundary between fuel and reflector. The Fig. 2 illustrates the normalized per unit dependence of the importance function on energy for the HMF028 variant.

In Table 1 experimental data (E) is compared with calculations performed in several variations. Firstly, the importance function is assumed to be constant throughout the phase space (C_0). Secondly, the importance function is represented in one- and 14-group approximations (C_1 and C_{14} , respectively). The statistical uncertainty in the calculation of kinetic functionals is less than 0.1%, and some deviation in the tallies can be explained by uncertainty in the cross sections. As evidenced by the findings the consideration of the energy dependence of the importance function exerts a negligible influence on the derived values of β_{eff} and Λ in the examined variants.

In order to provide an explanation for this circumstance the central region of the HMF001 variant should be considered. It has been established that the vast majority of prompt neutrons are generated in the range from 100 keV to 6.5 MeV, with delayed neutrons being generated from 46.5 keV to 1.4 MeV. As demonstrated in Fig. 3, the importance function in this range exhibits negligible variation, with its values averaged over two spectra differing by approximately 2%. Consequently, the discrepancies between the single-group and multi-group approaches in this problem are negligible.

Figure 2. Importance function spectrum for different areas of HMF028 variant. **A.** Fuel (center); **B.** Fuel (outer surface); **C.** Reflector (inner surface); **D.** Reflector (outer surface).

Figure 3. Energy dependencies. **A.** Delayed generation density; **B.** Prompt neutron generation density; **C.** Importance function.

Conclusion

An original approach for calculating the multi-group neutron importance function based on the matrix method has been developed for the MCU code.

The methodology is predicated on the division of the calculation model into a finite number of tally objects and

energy groups. In the course of the modelling process the elements of the block fission matrix \mathbf{T} are tallied. In the post-processing stage this matrix is utilized to calculate an eigenvector, the elements of which represent the importance of a neutron born in a specific object and energy group. The resulting importance function can then be used repeatedly in the calculations of various functionals.

Six benchmarks from the ICSBEP Handbook were calculated to validate the method. The comparison of the results obtained for the single-group and 14-group approximations shows the difference of less than 1%, which is due to a minor alteration in the importance function in the energy intervals where the primary (more than 95%) generation of both prompt and delayed neutrons occurs. The discrepancy between the importance functions, when averaged over the spectrum of delayed and prompt neutron generation, is less than 2%.

The calculation results demonstrate a high degree of agreement with the experiment. It has been demonstrated that, within the scope of the benchmarks considered in this work, there is no necessity in taking into account the energy dependence of the importance function.

The work was carried out within the state assignment of NRC “Kurchatov Institute”.

References

- Abagyan LP, Bazazyanz NO, Nikolaev MN, Tsybulya AM (1981) Gruppovye Konstanty Dlya Rascheta Reaktorov i Zashchity. Energoizdat, Moscow, 232 pp. [in Russian]
- Arkhangelsky DM, Daichenkova YuS, Kalugin MA, Oleynik DS, Shkarovsky DA (2023) The effect of the importance function resolution on the accuracy of calculating the functionals of the neutron kinetics in water critical assemblies by Monte Carlo method. Nuclear Energy and Technology 9(3): 171–175. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.9.112165>
- Bell D, Glasstone S (1974) Teoriya yadernikh reaktorov. Aromizdat, Moscow, 496 pp. [in Russian]
- Belousov VI, Gomin EA, Davidenko VD, Dyachkov II, Ioannisian MV, Raskach KF, Pisarev AN (2024) Algorithms for Calculating the Effective Parameters of the Point Kinetics Equations Based on the Monte Carlo Method, their Verification and Validation. Voprosy atomnoy nauki i tekhniki. Serya: Fizika yadernikh reaktorov 1: 19–31. [in Russian] <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1063778825080046>
- Carney S, Brown F, Kiedrowski B, Martin W (2014) Theory and applications of the fission matrix method for continuous-energy Monte Carlo. Annals of Nuclear Energy 73: 423–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2014.07.020>
- Frank-Kamenetsky AD, Yudkevich MS (1971) Raschet vremeni zhizni mgnovennykh neitronov v reaktore metodom Monte-Karlo. Preprint IAE-2155, Moscow, 13 pp. [in Russian]
- Gurevich MI, Kalugin MA, Oleynik DS, Shkarovsky DA (2019) Estimation of some neutron physics characteristics by Monte-Carlo method using the importance function. Annals of Nuclear Energy 130: 388–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.02.047>
- Hoogenboom J (2003) Methodology of Continuous-Energy Adjoint Monte Carlo for Neutron, Photon, and Coupled Neutron-Photon Transport. Nuclear Science and Engineering 143(2): 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE03-A2322>
- Hurwitz H (1964) Physical Interpretation of the Adjoint Flux: Iterated Fission Probability. Naval Reactor Physics Handbook, 864–869.
- Ilyin VA, Poznyak EG (1999) Lineynaya algebra. Nauka. Fizmatlit, Moscow, 296 pp. [in Russian]
- Kiedrowski B, Brown F, Wilson P (2011) Adjoint-Weighted Tallies for k-Eigenvalue Calculations with Continuous-Energy Monte Carlo. Nuclear Science and Engineering 168(3): 226–241. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE10-22>
- Leppänen J, Aufiero M, Fridman E, Rachamin R, van der Marck S (2014) Calculation of effective point kinetics parameters in the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code. Annals of Nuclear Energy 65: 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2013.10.032>
- Meulekamp R, Marck S (2006) Calculating the Effective Delayed Neutron Fraction with Monte Carlo. Nuclear Science and Engineering 152(2): 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE03-107>
- Nagaya Y, Chiba G, Mori T, Irwanto D, Nakajima K (2010) Comparison of Monte Carlo calculation methods for effective delayed neutron fraction. Annals of Nuclear Energy 37(10): 1308–1315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2010.05.017>
- Nauchi Y, Kameyama T (2010) Development of Calculation Technique for Iterated Fission Probability and Reactor Kinetic Parameters Using Continuous-Energy Monte Carlo Method. Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology 47(11): 977–990. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18811248.2010.9711662>

- Paxton H (1981) Fast critical experiments. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 7(3): 151-174. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0149-1970\(81\)90030-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0149-1970(81)90030-5)
- Peng X, Liang J, Forget B, Smith K (2019) Calculation of adjoint-weighted reactor kinetics parameters in OpenMC. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 128: 231–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.01.007>
- Peng X, Liang J, Alhajri A, Forget B, Smith K (2017) Development of continuous-energy sensitivity analysis capability in OpenMC. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 110: 362-383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2017.06.061>
- Perfetti C, Rearden T, Martin W (2017) SCALE Continuous-Energy and Eigenvalue Sensitivity and Coefficient Calculations. *Nuclear Science and Engineering* 182: 332–353. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE15-12>
- Qiu Y, Wang Z, Li K, Yuan Y, Wang K, Fratoni M (2017) Calculation of adjoint-weighted kinetic parameters with the reactor Monte Carlo code RMC. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 101: 424-434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2017.03.023>